

Rural access and connectivity

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Rural connectivity is a relevant factor for equitable progress in Latin America and the Caribbean. And although universalizing access to technologies does not guarantee their full use, it is expected that the expansion of Internet coverage plus training in digital skills will lead to a qualitative leap towards equitable progress.

Now that the internet is a key condition for citizens to have access to essential public services, it is important to improve media literacy in order to make digitalization an opportunity for development, in line with the goals set by the United Nations in the SDGs.

Those who do not have access to the global network do not have access to rights and services, which is why there is an urgent need to retrain the economically active population because it means employment opportunities. On the other hand, strengthening the participation of citizens in the construction of a broad public opinion implies addressing rural diversity, as well as building information competencies, particularly among women and young people.

It is alarming that 72 million inhabitants of Latin America and the Caribbean do not have access to good rural connectivity, according to SELA. Digital divides are identified according to age, gender, socio-economic status, mother tongue and geographic location, between rural and urban areas. These data confirm the fact that poverty is stronger in non-urban areas.

An immediate aim of states and supranational bodies is to overcome the difficulties because the potential benefits of information for freedom of expression, governance and growth; and for achieving objective terms of trade in the emerging knowledge economies are known.

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